

The figure illustrates the YSB rearing procedure. Six hills of 14-d-old IR62 seedlings are transplanted weekly in a 34- × 25- × 11-cm plastic basin containing rice soil. At booting stage, about 63 d after sowing, tillers with bulging leaf sheaths are infested with 2 larvae/tiller. A 2.5-cm slit is cut along the midportion of the bulging leaf sheath. The incision is opened by spreading the cut edges to about 1 cm, which exposes a small section of the growing panicle. The slit is held open and YSB larvae are placed on the exposed panicle with a camel hair brush. When the edges of the slit close, the insects are trapped inside the boot. There should be no smoking during this procedure because newly hatched YSB larvae are highly sensitive to tobacco smoke.

Infested plants are placed in a 1.5- × 5.5- × 0.15-m water pan tray inside a large screen room. The water provides moisture for the plants and prevents ants from feeding on the insects. When the larvae have pupated at 25-30 d after infestation (DI) the plants are cut to 15-cm height and transferred to an adult emergence cage in another water pan tray. When adults emerge at 31-40 DI they are transferred to an oviposition cage containing 40- to 45-d-old potted TN1 plants. The YSB lay eggs on TN1 1-2 d after emergence.

Potted plants with egg masses are collected daily (32-41 DI) and placed in a water pan tray. To maintain the culture, the leaves of the TN1 plants with egg masses laid at 36 DI are cut into small pieces 4 d after oviposition. The leaf pieces are placed in test tubes or ball jars with moist cotton at the bottom. The eggs hatch at 42 DI. Larvae are then placed on booting plants and the cycle is repeated.

To provide larvae for experiments, cut leaves with egg masses at 32-35 DI and

Steps in rearing YSB for resistance studies. DI = d after infestation.

37-41 DI are placed in test tubes. The hatching larvae are for varietal screening for resistance or for basic studies of resistance mechanisms.

With these procedures, about 80% of all infested tillers produce an adult moth.

Each week at IRRI, we infest 10 plastic containers, each with 6 hills of 63-d-old plants, to maintain the insect culture and to infest 1 concrete bed (2.5 × 26 m) of about 1,500 30-d-old test plants for screening cultivars for resistance. □

Life cycle of *Marasmia patnalis*, a rice leaffolder in the Philippines

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From Oct to Mar 1984, larvae of *M.*

patnalis Bradley (Lepidoptera:Pyralidae), identified by A. T. Barrion of IRRI, were observed folding and damaging rice leaves on the IRRI experiment farm. This leaffolder species is widely distributed in Southeast Asia. However, it has escaped the attention of rice entomologists

because the larva and adult, larval behavioral habits, and plant damage symptoms closely resemble those of the more commonly known leaffolder, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

We studied the life cycle of *M. patnalis* in the greenhouse at 26-34°C and 70-80%

relative humidity. Gravid female moths collected from the field were the source of insects. Females laid eggs singly or in groups of 2-9 on upper and lower rice leaf surfaces, but mostly on the upper leaves touching the margins of the main veins. Groups of two eggs were most common. Sometimes, eggs were laid on leaf sheaths. Incubation took 4 d (see table). The first-instar larvae fed in groups. They scraped the leaf surface and preferred young seedlings. The second-instar larvae folded leaves and fed within the fold. Feeding was always on parenchyma cells (between veins). No feeding was observed on

bundle sheath and sclerenchyma cells. The larvae passed through 6 instars in 23 d.

Pupation occurred within a silken cocoon, most commonly between two adjacent leaves tied together with silk. Pupation also occurred at the basal part of the inner tillers and lasted 9 d.

Adult emergence was most frequent from 2200 to 2400 h. Male:female was 2:1 (n=80). Females laid about 120 eggs. Total development period and percent survival at different stages of development are in the table. □

Life cycle of the rice leaf folder *Marasmia patnalis* reared on TN1, IRR1 greenhouse, 1984.

Character	Duration ^a (d)		Survival (%)
	Av	Range	
Egg	4	4-5	92
Larva	23	21-25	88
Prepupa	1	1-2	^b
Pupa	9	7-11	74
Total development period	37	33-43	
Adult longevity			
Male	3	4-3	
Female	5	6-7	

^a n = 60 males and 60 females. ^b No data.

Effect of sequential release of resistant rices on brown planthopper (BPH) biotype development in the Solomon Islands

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New BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål biotypes on some varieties may develop in six to nine generations in laboratory tests. In the Solomon Islands, planting varieties with different resistance genes for the last 10 yr produced a highly virulent BPH population,

IRRI resistant varieties were introduced in 1974. IR26, IR28, IR30, IR1628, and GPL 2S were planted from 1974 to 1977, until BPH biotype 2 developed (Table 1). IR36 and IR42 were planted in 1978, but were phased out because of susceptibility to leafroller *Susumia exigua* and root rot. Mala was then planted until 1981.

Field screening in 1980 indicated that BPH biotype 2 was dominant. In mid-1984, BG379-5 suffered heavy hopperburn and was replaced by resistant MTU5249, which is still planted. In 1984 seedling screening, BPH biotype 3 was identified (Table 2). ASD7 and BG379-5 were susceptible, but Ptb 33 was only slightly damaged.

As BPH biotypes have changed, fewer varieties of the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) of the International Rice Testing Program have maintained BPH resistance in the Solomon Islands. Only 12% of the 1984 IRBPHN

Table 1. Effects of sequential release of resistant rice varieties on BPH biotype development in the Solomon Islands, 1974-84.

Year	Variety	Resistance gene	Virulence ^a	Remarks
1974	IR26	<i>Bph 1</i>	Biotype 2	Susceptible
1975	IR1628	Unknown	—	Susceptible to sclerotinia root rot
1976	IR28, IR30, GPL 2S	<i>Bph 1</i>	Biotype 2	—
1977	BG94-1	Unknown	—	Susceptible to leafroller
1978	IR36	— <i>bph 2</i>	—	IR36 and IR42 were used in only 2 croppings and were very susceptible to leafroller
	IR42	— <i>bph 2</i>		
1979	Mala	Unknown	—	—
1980	IR42, Mala	—	Biotype 2 ^b	Hopperburned in late 1980, but tolerant of high <i>N. lugens</i> population
	Mala	—	—	Hopperburned in March 1984
Early 1982	BG379-5	Unknown	—	—
1984	BG379-5	—	—	—
	IR9852-22-3	Unknown (with IR36 as parent)	Biotype 3	—

^a *N. lugens* virulence at the end of the resistance life. ^b As ASD7, resistant in 1980.

Table 2. Results of seedling bulk test for BPH resistance in November 1984^a, Solomon Islands.

Variety	Score ^b	Remarks
TN1	9	Susceptible check
Mudgo	9	<i>Bph 1</i>
ASD7	9	<i>bph 2</i>
Ptb 33	3.6	<i>Bph 3</i>
Babawee	7	<i>bph 4</i>
MTU5249	1.6	Parentage: MTU4569/ARC6650 currently resistant commercial variety
BG379-5	9	Parentage: BG96-3*2/Ptb33, commercial variety from 1982 to March 1984
ARC6650	1.6	Parent of MTU5 249
BG367-2	.3	Parentage: BG280-1*2/Ptb 33, most resistant variety in 1984 IRBPHN

^a Av of 3 replications. Screening made in seedboxes using *N. lugens* from commercial fields. Seedlings were infested with nymphs and adults 9 d after germination. ^b Scored according to 0-9 scale of the Standard evaluation system for rice.

were moderately to highly resistant to our present BPH population, compared with 39% in 1980.

The quick breakdown in resistant varieties was caused by several factors: 1) intensive staggered cropping within a